

On the Role of Synthetic Chemistry in Chemotherapy

U. P. Basu

BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH INSTITUTE, CALCUTTA

Organic chemistry has advanced considerably during the last 50 years. The creative function of organic chemistry is supplementing Nature to help mankind in maintaining health and combating disease. Systematic research on medicaments has much widened the frontiers of Science. With the advance of knowledge in natural sciences, studies on the composition and constitution of the natural products were undertaken. Hundreds of alkaloids (about 950) are known to-day and yet according to Willaman and Schubert¹ only 2% of all species of plants has so far been tested for their alkaloid content. Many of the known alkaloids have been synthesised. The historic development of our knowledge in the field of alkaloids is summarized in Table I.

TABLE I

Alkaloid.	Isolation.	Structure evaluation	Synthesis.
Morphine	1817 (1804)	1927	1952
Strychnine	1818	1947	1954
Quinine	1820	1909	1944
Nicotine	1828	1895	1900
Atropine	1834	1898	1904
Papaverine	1847	1886	1909
Aconitine	1856	..	..
Cocaine	1860	1898	1902
Ephedrine	1885	1909	1925
Lobeline	1920	1928	1929
Ergotamine	1922	1951	..

While it took over a century to synthesise these few alkaloids, synthetic organic chemistry has made rapid progress and new synthetic drugs keep on appearing in increasing numbers at frequent intervals. One of the latest biologically active alkaloids is reserpine, first isolated in 1952 from the Indian plant *Rauwolfia serpentina*, and synthesised in 1956. It is an indole derivative (I) containing a trimethoxybenzoyl grouping interlinked through a complex cyclic chain to the indole part of the molecule.

The observation of Crongeim *et al.*² on the sedative action of trimoglamide, trimethoxybenzoyl glycine diethylamide (II), on human subjects tends to show the role of modern techniques in the synthesis of structural analogues of natural drugs. A survey of literature

would show that many analogues of alkaloids have been synthesised by the organic chemists and their specific biological activities established by collaboration with the biologists.

The local anaesthetic, cocaine, the constitution of which was established in 1898, was practically replaced in 1905 by the simpler substance, procaine. The alkaloid, morphine, is now being replaced to an extent by pethidine, the activity of which was revealed after thirteen years of establishment of the structure of morphine³. All these examples tend to support the suggestion that synthesis for its own sake may be continued on a planned basis and this may reveal products of outstanding utility in health and disease.

Newer Advances

With the development of our knowledge in chemistry (particularly organic chemistry) and with the expansion of the methods of technique in pharmacology, attempts for synthesising newer products having no relation with the natural analogues have been made with significant success in several directions. Work in the fields of antipyretics and analgesics is too well known. Similarly, hypnotics, sedatives, and anticonvulsants were discovered in barbituric acids, amides, ureides, and hydantoin. The interesting findings of vasoactive response of nikethamide and cardiazole are a distinct contribution of synthetic chemists to medicine. More ingenuity came to be borne on such investigations since the introduction into bacteriology of staining methods using organic dyes. Ehrlich in 1881 described the staining of bacteria with methylene blue and in the year 1891 he demonstrated the activities of methylene blue on malaria parasites. Quinine has been in use as a chemotherapeutic agent against malarial infections. Once it was realized that a synthetic product might be effective in combating bacteria as well as protozoa, development of chemotherapy proceeded rapidly and synthetic drugs, which had no relation with the naturally-occurring biological agents, were introduced in clinical practice. In this connection, chiniofon and iodochlorohydroxyquinoline may be mentioned as the earlier agents introduced for the treatment of amoebic dysentery which, however, still needs a better and more effective drug.

The failure of quinine to cure all forms of malaria gave an impetus to extensive studies aimed at the discovery of a product better than quinine; plasmochin was introduced in 1924 and atabrin in 1933. Introduction of the potent antimalarial, paludrine, during

the war period was a triumph of modern synthetic chemistry in the field of drug design. The current drug of choice is, however, chloroquine. Chemical structures of all these products would, however, indicate that synthetic chemists have been successful in preparing products with equivalent or even better biological activity, much simpler in constitution than those produced by nature.

In spite of these spectacular advances, the progress in combating infections of bacterial origin was slow in the early stages. The synthesis of prontosil by Mietsch and Klarer in the Elderfield laboratory of Bayer and its efficacy in the streptococcal infection, as demonstrated by Domagk in early thirties of this century, opened up a new field for synthetic chemists. Everyone is now familiar with sulfa drugs that have helped in controlling the scourges caused by many pathogenic bacteria. While treatment of various diseases with synthetic chemotherapeutic agents was playing a predominant role in the medical field, the discovery of the powerful antibiotics, penicillin, tetracycline, aureomycin, and streptomycin, brought the substances of natural origin in limelight again. The speciality of penicillin lies in its four-membered lactam ring condensed with a sulphur containing five-membered ring (III) and that of streptomycin in its peculiar guanidine structure (IV). These antibiotics possess a wide spectrum of biological activity; the former is effective against gram-positive and the latter against gram-negative organisms. Taking advantages of easy screening methods, now available, the synthetic chemists have produced newer derivatives of sulphonamide to combat infections of the former type, and simpler compounds like *para*-aminosalicylic acid, isonicotinic acid hydrazide, and sulphones to control the latter. Thus it is found that natural compounds are being successfully substituted by synthetic products.

Problems to be Solved

Infectious diseases are now controlled in the West largely by public health measures. It is expected that in our country also, with the improvement of our economic level and with the maintenance of healthy conditions of our environments, incidence of infectious diseases will be reduced appreciably. In the developed countries of the world, heart disease (to which vascular lesions of the central nervous system are added) and cancer are responsible for the highest number of deaths. Treatment of these ailments has become a challenge to those interested in evolving synthetic medicaments. Difficulty in the production of anticancer drugs is due to the fact that neither the mode of formation of cancer cells, nor the law of their spreading is clearly known. In cancerous growth the rate of cell division (mitosis) is abnormally high. Either the formation of the abnormal cells or the mitosis has to be checked. Difficulty in evolving any synthetic medicament in this case, is that one has to deal not

with an invading pathogenic organism foreign to the body, but with the host's own tissues. Undesirable growth has to be controlled without affecting the normal cells. It is known that the change from normal to malignant transformation may be stimulated by numerous chemical, physical, and biological agents, but the nature of this change is not very clear. The nucleus of the cell contains polymers composed of nucleotides, known as deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and it is believed that a derangement of the native DNA is the cause of cancer. Prevention of such derangement becomes the problem.

The chemotherapy of cancer is a very complicated problem and more than 40,000 chemicals are screened every year in the United States of America for anticancer activity. Numerous compounds of varied nature have been and are being synthesised for biological testing. Different compounds in the nitrogen mustard series have been studied. The first compounds used against cancer was methyl-bis-(β -chloroethyl)amine. Substitution of the methyl group in this compound by various other groups, particularly those containing peptide linkages, have been found to combine with most cell constituents, and to inhibit many enzyme systems including choline oxidase, choline esterase, and pyruvic acid oxidase.

Products of divergent nature are being tried in search for a suitable compound to combat malignant growth in bone, skin, glands, and heart or the tumours of lipoid processes, but none has so far been found to be an ideal chemotherapeutic agent. In Hodgkin's disease, lymphosarcoma, and lymphocytic leukemia interesting observations are on record from a study with ethylenimines. The product that has been more extensively studied is 2, 4, 6-tris-(ethylenimino)-s-triazine. This compound, commonly known as TEM, has a profound inhibitory action on the progress of human cancer; but with nitrogen mustard the cancerous cells tend ultimately to be refractory to this compound. It is of interest to note that the antimalarial (supazine), worked out in this Institute, is also a triazine derivative, but it has not been tested for anticancer activity.

Among the natural products colchicine derivatives have been tried, but the problem lies in controlling the formation and regulation of cell and its constituents. It has not yet been elucidated how the change from the normal to the malignant cell takes place.

Brilliant successes have been achieved in the treatment of bacterial, protozoal and spirochaetal infections, but we do not know the fundamental biochemistry of the microorganisms, the nature of the various enzymatic reactions in the system, nor anything about their integrated functioning in the living cell. Although we have been able to control the infectious diseases and prolong life expectancy, we are in difficulty in controlling the disorders produced by virus infections or cancer or, with heart diseases, which are responsible for the maximum number of deaths in the developed countries of the world. Attempts are being made to synthesise chemical compounds to combat these conditions also.

In order to deal with the treatment of heart diseases, one has to consider the biochemical reactions that are going on in the system. The essential phases of cardiac metabolism are energy production and energy liberation. The former involves oxidation of our food materials, and the latter relates more to protein functioning and various enzyme reactions. We do not know all changes that are going on *in vivo*. We cannot also fix our diet, environmental conditions, and other habits, and as such who knows whether the breakdown products of our heterogeneous food may be the factors in controlling the physiology of the system. Many pressor amines are being formed, oxidised and/or converted to

different products to exert one or other physiological phenomenon. Our food protein, casein, contains an amino-acid, tryptophan, which is known to form vaso-active (pressor) amines-tryptamine or serotonin. Under the influence of the monoamine oxidase (as enzyme present in liver) they may undergo oxidation to aldehyde of the type (V). This aldehyde may easily react with the naturally-occurring monoamines (for example, dopamine) to give rise to products (VI) bearing a close relationship to indoles to which group many psychotropic drugs like harmine (VII), yohimbine (VIII), and reserpine (I) belong.

As a matter of fact, tryptophan has been converted in the laboratory to afford harman. In nature various enzymes play a role in many biochemical reactions and help in the formation of different components in the system to exert pharmacological action. Recent discoveries have revealed that the naturally-occurring active substances, vasopressin, insulin, glucagon, and hypertensin, are compounds of peptide nature. Thus, the synthetic chemists find new fields for investigation. As a matter of course, organic chemists have already synthesised a number of compounds that are helping in producing a prolonged lowering of the tension. Amongst these mention may be made of chlorpromazine⁴ (phenothiazine derivative), hydroxyzine (diphenylmethane derivative) hydrazino-phthalazine, mephesisin (propane-diol derivative) and hydrochlorothiazide. These are products of diverse

nature, but they all exert therapeutic action in the same disorder. Influence of a drug in man as a whole would be of complicated nature, but the modern tracer methods may help the biologists in offering their suggestion to chemists for the synthesis of novel structures to reveal newer chemotherapeutic compounds.

Synthetic chemistry is receiving profound significance from the rapidly progressing elucidation of biosynthesis in Nature, and newer developments in operating science. We now know that hormones formed in our body can influence the psychic and mental behaviour. We know that our food proteins provide both stimulants as well as depressing agents. It is difficult to predict any future development. We have already discovered many drugs to mitigate our miseries, but the aspiration of synthetic chemists is now to control the symptoms of ageing. With the help of the physical and biological aids, organic chemists may help in the isolation of products that play decisive role in proper functioning of the body and subsequently, in the production of chemotherapeutic products to control various disorders that are being noticed amongst people living under stress and strain of modern civilization.

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